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RADIOXENON RELEASE FROM A HIROSHIMA-SIZED NUCLEAR EXPLOSION

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ABSTRACT

This study focuses on the evaluation of radio xenon released following a Hiroshima-sized nuclear weapon explosion. Certain xenon isotopes, namely Xe135, Xe133m, Xe133 and The method consists of using radioactive evaluation data from Evaluated Nuclear Structure Data File (ENSDF). These data include the radioactive decay constant and half-life. Measurement data from real observations including Nevada underground nuclear test and Fukushima accident debris are also used. Appropriated calculation algorithms describing the radioactive evolution of the isotopes in consideration are used to evaluate the change over time of the radioxenon isotopic activity ratios. It appears that an isotopic activity of 1 million Tetra Becquerel (TBq) was reached by Xe135 two weeks after the explosion.

KEYWORDS: *Nuclear explosion, Radioxenon, Hiroshima-sized nuclear weapon, Radioactivity.***1. INTRODUCTION**

Nuclear energy is used in several areas, both civil and military. In the military field, it is mainly used in nuclear weapons through nuclear explosive devices, the best known of which are nuclear bombs. The real use of thermonuclear energy in the form of an atomic bomb during the Second World War was materialized by the detonation of two bombs, one on Hiroshima on August 6, 1945 and the second on Nagasaki on August 9 of the same year. Following the detonation of a nuclear explosive device, several radionuclides, called fissions products, are produced and contained in the radioactive fallout, including isotopes of xenon. Xenon isotopes such as Xe131m, Xe133m, Xe133 and Xe135 are of interest for the characterization of nuclear events (DE GEER L.-E. et al., 2001) as part of the verification activities of the National Nuclear Data Center (NDC) of Burkina Faso based at the National Center for Scientific and Technological Research (CNRST).

The Hiroshima nuclear explosion was caused by a nuclear device called Little Boy and using insertion A-bomb technology. It took Little Boy approximately 45 seconds to descend to an altitude of 1,900 feet (580 m), at which point it exploded in the sky directly above Shima Hospital. Less than a millisecond after the explosion, the temperature at ground level exceeded 7,000 °C (12,600 °F) and a powerful blast wave swept across the landscape. The enormous mushroom cloud rose to an altitude of more than 12 km. In Little Boy, it is reported that less than 2% of the uranium-235 reached fission and the explosive force was equivalent to 15,000 tons of TNT (Casey-Maslen, 2021) (Barnaby, 1995; Glasstone, 1964) (Britannica, The Editors of Encyclopaedia, 2023).

The Hiroshima nuclear explosion using insertion A-bomb technology, the fission process starts by projecting a block of uranium 235 onto another block in order to reach critical mass.

This work estimates by using decay algorithms how much radioxenon is produced in a Hiroshima-sized nuclear weapon explosion. The evaluation of this quantity of radioxenon can be used to understand the variability of data

measured as part of a verification of the occurrence of a nuclear test by the Comprehensive Nuclear-Test-Ban Treaty Organization (CTBTO).

2. MATERIALS AND METHODS

Evaluating the quantity of radioxenon released requires knowing the radionuclides involved in the xenon decay process. The differential equations describing the decay over time in the nuclear test with full fractionation and limited to the four CTBT relevant isotopes/isomers can be given as follow:

$$\frac{dN_1(t)}{dt} = -\lambda_1 \cdot N_1(t), \quad N_1(t = 0) = N_1^0 \neq 0 \quad (i)$$

$$\frac{dN_2(t)}{dt} = -\lambda_2 \cdot N_2(t) + \lambda_1 \cdot N_1(t), \quad N_2(t = 0) = N_2^0 \neq 0 \quad (ii)$$

$N(t)$: Number of nuclides;

λ : Decay constant

t : Time

(2) refers to ^{131m}Xe , ^{133m}Xe and ^{135}Xe ;

(3) refers to ^{133}Xe with index 1 for ^{133}Xe and index 2 for ^{133m}Xe .

Figure 1 shows the decay chains giving the radioxenon Xe-135, Xe-133m, Xe-133 and Xe-131m in growth condition.

Figure 1: Radioactive decay chains of the radioxenon of interest.

As we can see in Figure 1, the determination of the isotopic activity of Xe-135, Xe-133m (and Xe-133) and Xe-131m takes necessarily into account the decay of their precursors. The three decay chains start with tin (Sn-135), indium (In-133) and cadmium (Cd-131) respectively.

Isotopes and isomers are not included in the differential equations, if their independent fission yield is smaller than 10^{-10} . For example, the 135 chain could start with In-135 that has a half-life $T = (9.2000 \pm 1.0000)10^{-2}$ seconds, a branching ratio of the Beta-minus mode $P_{In-135,Sn-135} = 0.0000$ percent and an independent fission yield $Y_{ind.} = (7.2554 \pm 4.6435)10^{-11}$. In considering the low value of the fission yield, this nuclide can be ignored.

Isomers with a very short half-life are removed from the differential equations and their contribution represented in an appropriate way. In the 133 chain, the nuclide I-133m having a half-life $T = (9.000 \pm 2.0000)$ seconds is taken into account in the initial amount of I-133 with a half-life $T = (7.4880 \pm 0.0360)10^{+4}$ seconds and the branching of Te-133m that has a half-life $T = (3.3240 \pm 0.0240)10^{+3}$ seconds is corrected by taking into consideration the branching factor $P_{Tem-133,I-133}$. For the 131 chain, the nuclide Sn-131m with a half-life $T = (5.8400 \pm 0.0500)10^{+1}$ seconds is taken into account in the initial amount of Sn-131.

The explosion led to the release of significant quantities of radionuclides into the environment, and among these radionuclides the xenon isotopes Xe131m, Xe133m, Xe133 and Xe135. The evaluation of the quantity of radioxenon released by this explosion requires the use of:

- Radioactive evaluation data, particularly the radioactive half-life and the decay or decay constant (NDS - IAEA, 2011) ;
- Measurement data from real observations from measuring instruments. Gamma spectrometry with a hyperpure germanium detector (Becker et al., 2010).
- Appropriate calculation algorithms describing the radioactive evolution of the isotopes in consideration. The analytical formulas giving the isotopic activities in a nuclear explosion situation can be found in (Yamba et al., 2018).

The explosive power of the bomb used on Hiroshima was estimated at approximately 13 Kt TNT-equivalent. 1 Kt TNT-equivalent corresponds to the energy released by the explosion of 1,000 tons of TNT, or approximately 2.611448×10^{25} Mev.

3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Some radioxenon isotopes such as ^{135}Xe , $^{133\text{m}}\text{Xe}$, ^{133}Xe and $^{131\text{m}}\text{Xe}$ are considered as relevant for CTBT nuclear explosion monitoring. Remote detections of an underground nuclear test are most likely associated with a sudden release (a prompt or delayed but short-term release) of fission products (Kalinowski, 2011). We can consider two extreme kinds of sudden releases: radioactivity release full fractionation of gaseous fission products from their precursors and radioactivity release a composition that developed under in-growth condition. In the first case, xenon gas escapes immediately after the end of fission reactions; and in the second case, xenon gas stay mixed with its precursors until being released.

The comprehensive analytical solution giving the numbers of nuclides of interest $N_{Xe135}(t)$, $N_{Xe133}(t)$, $N_{Xe133\text{m}}(t)$, $N_{Xe131\text{m}}(t)$ used in this work can be found in (Yamba et al., 2018).

The change over time of isotopic activity ratios of the radioxenons of interest is given in Figure 2 that is an update of similar plots published in (Kalinowski et al., 2010).

Figure 2: The change over time of isotopic activity ratios of CTBT-relevant radionuclides for nuclear explosion under in-growth condition, nuclear explosion with full fractionation, release from NPP and MIPF.

The isotopic activity resulting from the explosion of a Hiroshima-sized nuclear weapon is evaluated using uranium (U-235) as fissile material. Figure 4 gives an overview of the evolution over time of isotopic activity due to the release of radionuclides. We notice in this figure that just a few seconds after the detonation of the nuclear weapon, the element Xe135 is the one with the highest isotopic activity with a value of approximately 100,000 TBq. While the lowest value of isotopic activity corresponds to Xe131m having an isotopic activity of approximately 0.05 TBq. The highest isotopic activity value over time of approximately 1 million TBq corresponds to Xe135 and this value is reached 15 days after the explosion.

Figure 3 gives an overview of the variation in relative isotopic activity of the event studied. We note that over time, Xe135, Xe133 and Xe131m represent, in this order, approximately 95% of the total activity of the mixture.

Change over time of the Radionuclide Isotopic activity from a Hiroshima-sized nuclear weapon explosion

Figure 3 : Isotopic activity of radionuclides Xe135, Xe133m, Xe133 and Xe131m from a Hiroshima-sized explosion.

Figure 4 gives an overview of the variation in relative isotopic activity of the event studied. We can notice that over time, Xe135, Xe133 and Xe131m represent, in this order, approximately 95% of the total activity of the mixture.

Figure 4 : Relative isotopic activity of radionuclides Xe135, Xe133m, Xe133 and Xe131m from a Hiroshima-sized explosion
 A comparison with the scenario of a Nagasaki-sized nuclear explosion was made. The Nagasaki nuclear explosion was due to a nuclear device called Fat Man and using A-bomb technology. The fissile material used in this device is plutonium 239 (Pu-239). The Fat Man explosion led to the release of a large quantity of radionuclides into the environment, and among these radionuclides are the xenon isotopes Xe131m, Xe133m, Xe133 and Xe135. Fat Man's explosive power was estimated at approximately 21 Kt TNT-equivalent. 1 Kt TNT-equivalent corresponds to the energy released by the explosion of 1,000 tonnes of TNT, or approximately 2.611448×10^{25} Mev.

Figure 5 shows the comparison of the release radionuclides between Hiroshima and Nagasaki –sized nuclear weapon explosion. We notice that just a few seconds after the detonation of the Fat Man, Xe135 is the element with the highest isotopic activity with a value of approximately 100,000 TBq. The maximum isotopic activity reached of approximately 5 million TBq is that of Xe135 two weeks after the explosion as we can see in figure 5.

Figure 5: comparison of the release radionuclides between Hiroshima and Nagasaki –sized nuclear weapon explosion

4. CONCLUSION

The evaluation of the quantity of radioxenon mainly the CTBT relevant isotopes Xe135, Xe133, Xe133m and Xe131m following a Hiroshima-sized nuclear weapon explosion shows a significant variation between the isotopes over time. An activity of around 1 million TBq is reached by Xe135 two weeks after the explosion. The comparison with a Nagasaki-sized nuclear weapon explosion was done by considering 239Pu as fissile material. An activity of 5 million TBq was reached by Xe135 two weeks after the explosion.

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